

An adaptive framework for assessing climate resilience in buildings

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Climate resilience assessment
Climate exposure analysis
Environmental adaptation
Resilient buildings

ABSTRACT

As global climates continue to evolve, the urgency to enhance built environments against environmental challenges becomes more pronounced. Inspired by the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)—a system for assessing a building's smart readiness—this study introduces a framework to assess and evaluate climate resilience in buildings. The framework assesses a building's ability to anticipate, prepare for, respond to, and recover from adverse climate-related events. It begins with a climate exposure analysis that examines certain hazards and incorporates historical weather data for a comprehensive exposure analysis. Based on this analysis, a structured and quantifiable approach is employed to assess and benchmark the resilience of different building typologies across several domains. The assessment is grounded in qualitative analysis through extensive literature research, institutional guidelines, and best practices. It also employs a dynamic weighting based on the exposure assessment of a building's location, assigning resilience importance according to the climate risks faced. Initially applied to two buildings in Athens, Greece, and Helsinki, Finland — locations with significantly different climatic characteristics — the framework was then tested in experimental simulations. These simulations highlight the framework's adaptability to different climatic conditions. Finally, we summarize the major findings of the research, emphasizing its importance in promoting climate-resilient building practices, supporting the inventory of building stock, and aiding decision-making against increasingly intense and frequent climate risks.

1. Introduction

1.1. Climate change and resilience

In recent years, climate change has posed unprecedented challenges, influencing various facets of daily life. A significant result stemming from climate change is the escalating frequency and severity of climate-related disasters [1]. These phenomena have had a profound effect on human safety and have resulted in significant economic loss. More specifically, over the past fifty years, Europe alone has witnessed 1672 climate hazard-induced disasters, causing an estimated 476.5 billion in economic damages, [2]. As climate change progresses, the frequency of extreme weather events, including extreme temperatures, droughts, storms, and floods, is expected to increase, thus, further endangering societies worldwide. Already in the past twenty years, compared to 1980–1999, floods and storms have seen an increase of 137% and 40% respectively, while the occurrence of extreme temperatures and droughts has also surged, showing increases of 232% and 28% accordingly [3]. The research conducted by [4] involving 571 European cities indicates a projected rise in heatwaves, with southern Europe facing a particularly sharp increase of 69% in the coming decades. The study

also estimates that future droughts could be fourteen times worse than the ones already experienced, while there is also a potential 50% surge in flooding incidents, mainly affecting northwest Europe.

Amidst these challenges, buildings play a crucial role as the primary defense against the impacts of climate hazards. Climate-resilient buildings are distinguished by their comprehensive approach to resilience, integrating strategic planning, design, construction, energy efficiency renovation and efficient operation [5–7]. This approach is designed to proactively anticipate, prepare for, and adapt to the ever-changing climate conditions that get increasingly severe and frequent each year [8,9]. The hallmark of such buildings lies in their robust ability to withstand, efficiently respond to, and rapidly recover from the disruptions caused by evolving climate conditions. Beyond ensuring structural integrity, climate resilience in buildings embodies a holistic strategy aimed at mitigating or averting the adverse impacts of both present and future climate challenges [10]. This strategy encompasses the safeguarding of the building's physical structure, the preservation of the surrounding natural environment, the protection of the valuable assets contained within, and most importantly, the well-being of its

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111869>

Received 5 April 2024; Received in revised form 8 July 2024; Accepted 21 July 2024

Available online 5 August 2024

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occupants [11]. Consequently, a climate-resilient building is one that embeds resilience into every facet of its lifecycle, from its initial conceptualization to its ongoing operation, thereby ensuring its capability to resist and rebound from the effects of climate variability and change. The European Commission's report [10] outlines best strategies to enhance building resilience and adaptation solutions for each priority hazard and underscores the importance of strategic design and infrastructure choices in bolstering building resilience to diverse climate hazards. Despite these insights, many buildings have yet to adopt any of the recommended measures and remain at risk. Research done by the EU's Joint Research Centre [12] indicates that approximately 80% of current buildings are expected to still be in use by 2050, with 75% of these buildings being energy inefficient. Further, a comprehensive study as part of the iNSPiRe project, detailed by [13], reveals that of the existing European residential stock currently inhabited, 53% was built before 1971. These factors play a pivotal role in the resilience of buildings to climate hazards, indicating that a significant number of Europe's structures are presently vulnerable.

There is thus, an urgent need to develop effective methods for assessing building resilience effectively. This involves, not only evaluating a building's ability to withstand climate hazards, but also identifying potential vulnerabilities that are crucial to the building's resilience and could significantly enhance it if addressed in time. One of the biggest obstacles in creating a methodology for assessing buildings' resilience is the need to ensure its effectiveness across various locations and weather conditions. This necessitates robustness to accommodate diverse environmental contexts to address different building types and vulnerabilities. It is also as important to analyze the building characteristics in a manner that is accessible to all users, without requiring expertise in the domain. To overcome this, it is essential to create a user-friendly methodology that simplifies data collection and analysis, enabling widespread application by individuals regardless of their expertise in the field.

Since climate change and its associated hazards are increasing in recognition over the past years, there is a growing body of research addressing climate resilience. As outlined in the next section, while there have been efforts to assess climate resilience, they primarily focus either on urban areas facing specific hazards or on offering a broader assessment of risk exposure to climate hazards. Some initiatives by the European Commission, such as the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), have also contributed to this issue, however, more extensive research is crucial since, by identifying vulnerabilities and enhancing resilience, buildings can not only withstand extreme weather conditions more effectively, but can also achieve greater energy efficiency. Consequently, the building sector can be designed and retrofitted to be more durable and efficient against such conditions, thus contributing to the overall human safety and the broader efforts to mitigate the impacts of climate change.

1.2. Background

Research is still growing in the subject of building resilience against climate hazards since it is a relatively new topic. However, even in the existing literature, there are several gaps that emphasize the importance of developing a novel methodology. Most papers focus on analyzing the building components and systems that contribute to its resilience, without delving into the creation of a complete system that integrates this information and rates a building's resilience based on its attributes. Some indicative examples can be seen here: [14] talk about how extreme weather can impact power systems and how these effects can be mitigated, [15] delve into water systems resilience when affected by heavy rainfall, [16] elucidate best requirements for building envelope characteristics to handle extreme cold conditions, [17] evaluate the influence of natural hazards on the life cycle assessment of reinforced concrete buildings and [18] examine how the building

envelope and urban heat island effects influence the indoor thermal environment.

It is also common to find assessing methodologies that focus on specific disasters like earthquakes or fires rather than encompassing climate hazards as a whole. An example can be seen in [19] paper, where a computational model has been devised to measure fire-resilience. [20] have also undertaken a similar approach, concentrating on methodologies for assessing seismic resilience. The studies of [21, 22] focus on the assessment of buildings' thermal resilience, with a particular emphasis on investigating how energy-efficient measures in the former, and passive cooling strategies in the latter, can mitigate the heat exposure risk. Notably, [22] study is centered on a specific case study, namely nursery homes in the US.

In parallel with the scientific research, tailored applications are being developed to calculate building resilience by leveraging information about building characteristics. For instance, there are web tools like [23–25], that offer the users the ability to gain insight into their building's resilience by filling a questionnaire regarding the building's structural characteristics. Although promising, these tools are location specific since they are based on Australia, and are thus tailored to the infrastructure used in the area. Additionally, the questionnaire in [24] requires verification from an expert in the domain, thus not enabling an easy and automated analysis.

Other tools like [26,27] provide exposure analysis to specific climate hazards or natural disasters. This is an essential step to evaluate a building's resilience, but these tools do not go deeper towards assessing resilience against climate hazards. A more similar approach can also be found in the SRI, which evaluates a building's performance in smart services. The results include a score which indicated how close a building is to smart readiness in terms of specific categories like heating, cooling etc. Although the goal is different to that of assessment of climate resilience, the approach is analogous. Overall, these tools represent significant progress towards assessing a building's resilience, however, they lack a standardized methodology that can be applied to any building, regardless of the type and location.

While existing studies have made valuable contributions to the understanding of building resilience, there still remains a pressing need for a more holistic approach to assess building resilience, especially given the challenges posed by climate change. In the following sections, this paper delves into the various aspects involved in measuring building resilience and seeks to elucidate the complexities of climate adaptation. The proposed approach begins with a vulnerability and risk assessment which entails evaluating the building's exposure to various hazards, both current and future. Then, this information is used to assign appropriate weights to the building's technical features, which are integral to the overall climate resilience assessment. The next step focuses on identifying key building characteristics, related to the building envelope, the energy and water systems, sustainability practices, life cycle assessment indicators and adaptation solutions, while making the assessment user-friendly and accurate through thorough research on relevant building characteristics.

Key highlights of our study include:

- Development of a comprehensive framework to evaluate building resilience to climate impacts.
- Implementation of an adaptive assessment approach utilizing data-driven climate exposure analysis.
- Application of the framework in two diverse climatic regions.
- Simulation-based evaluation of various building configurations to gauge their impact on resilience.

The rest of the document is organized as follows. The methodology section follows, where the proposed framework for assessing building resilience is detailed, including its adaptive model and how it assesses buildings' resilience across different domains. Case studies are then presented, illustrating the application of the framework in real-world scenarios as well as in simulated experimental scenarios. This helps

in understanding its practical results and the framework's ability to adapt to different climatic challenges. The discussion section addresses the implications and limitations of the methodology, offering a critical analysis of its applicability and areas for improvement. Finally, the conclusions succinctly summarize the key findings and emphasize the importance of the framework in promoting more resilient building practices in the face of climate change. This structured approach not only facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the proposed framework but also underscores its significance in enhancing the resilience of buildings against climate hazards.

2. Methodology

This study is inspired by the implementation of the SRI, which is in its pilot phase across several European Union countries. The SRI evaluates the smart readiness of buildings, functioning as a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) to translate complex data into simplified, overarching measures reflecting trends or statuses of specific phenomena [28]. More specifically, the SRI framework evaluates a building's smart capabilities using a catalogue of smart-ready service functionality levels and weightings. It employs a scoring system that rates the building's features across various domains, such as heating, cooling, lighting, and energy management. This assessment produces an overall score indicating the level of integration of smart technologies. Despite its utility, the realm of climate resilience for buildings is devoid of such KPIs that succinctly convey a building's resilience against climate hazards. A similar approach could be applied to assess the climate resilience of a building by evaluating a comprehensive list of its characteristics across various domains and operational practices, using a scoring system to produce an overall resilience score. To address this gap, we propose a Climate Resilience Index (CRI) designed to quantify building resilience on a 0 to 100 scale. This index aims to enhance decision-making within the building sector by offering stakeholders actionable insights into climate risks. Our approach introduces a dynamic model for assessing climate resilience, departing from the SRI's static geographical weighting. The building assessment is divided into six domains: building envelope, energy systems, water systems, resilience practices, sustainability practices, and site and location. This segmentation enables a detailed, domain-specific evaluation of climate resilience. The six domains are defined as follows:

- **Building Envelope:** This domain includes the physical components that separate the interior of the building from the exterior environment, such as walls, roofs, windows, and doors. It is crucial for maintaining indoor conditions and protecting against external climate impacts.
- **Energy Systems:** This domain encompasses the building's energy supply, distribution, and usage systems, including heating, ventilation, air conditioning (HVAC), and their possible smart appliances. It focuses on the efficiency and resilience of these systems in the face of climate hazards.
- **Water Systems:** This domain addresses the management of water resources within the building, including supply, usage, drainage, and wastewater systems.
- **Resilience Practices:** This domain includes the strategies and actions implemented to enhance the building's ability to withstand and recover from climate-related events. This may involve emergency preparedness, response plans, and adaptive measures.
- **Sustainability Practices:** This domain evaluates the building's adherence to sustainable practices that mitigate climate change, such as the use of green materials, waste reduction strategies, and overall environmental impact.
- **Site and Location:** This domain considers the geographical and environmental context of the building, including its location-specific climate risks, surrounding infrastructure, and landscape features that influence its vulnerability and resilience.

These domains were derived from our classification based on the EU-level technical guidance on adapting buildings to climate change [10]. While the EU document provides a comprehensive overview of adaptation measures, our classification was conducted to create domain-specific evaluations of climate resilience. The above-mentioned domains were based on the building solutions presented in the EU-level technical guidance on adapting buildings to climate change [10]. These solutions were classified to form the six domains outlined in this manuscript. Dynamic weighting, determined through an analysis of local climatic conditions, enables the CRI to provide a tailored assessment that accurately reflects a building's resilience potential. This framework accommodates variations in climatic conditions, ensuring a comprehensive and nuanced evaluation. Furthermore, the methodology extensively inventories and captures the impact of a building's structural and system characteristics, not only on its resilience to climate hazards. The overarching methodology is depicted in Fig. 1, illustrating the step-by-step process and the integration of dynamic weighting into the assessment.

The assessment process for a building's climate resilience is strategically structured into three key phases: firstly, determining the building's exposure to specific climate hazards; secondly, documenting the architectural and systemic features of the building; and finally, synthesizing this information to compute the building's comprehensive climate resilience score. This methodical approach ensures a holistic evaluation, focusing on both external challenges and intrinsic structural qualities. The initial step – climate exposure analysis – is pivotal, as it sets the foundation for the subsequent analysis by establishing the context within which the resilience of the building will be evaluated. The exposure analysis not only identifies the specific hazards to which the building is vulnerable but also quantifies this exposure, forming the basis for the adaptive weighting mechanism in the resilience assessment process. Concurrently, data is gathered regarding the inherent characteristics of the building within each domain. These domains, encapsulated within the framework, include aspects such as the building envelope, energy systems, water management practices, resilience and sustainability practices, and the site's geographical and locational attributes. For each domain, a list of characteristics relevant to climate resilience is compiled. Characteristics for analysis are selected based on their potential impact on the building's ability to withstand, adapt to, and/or recover from climate-related hazards. This section is underpinned by a granular approach, where each characteristic's contribution to overall resilience is scrutinized. A pivotal element of this methodology is the creation of a comprehensive table detailing the impact scores attributed to various building configurations concerning their contribution to climate resilience. This step adopts a holistic approach, akin to the SRI, to document building characteristics. It encompasses both the tangible aspects of the building and the adaptive features embedded in its design and operational systems. This dual focus allows for a comprehensive understanding of the building's inherent and potential resilience capacities. The impact scores serve as a quantitative measure of how different configurations enhance or detract from the building's resilience. Having a detailed understanding of the building's characteristics and the corresponding impact scores, the framework leverages the weights derived from the initial exposure analysis to calculate the overall climate resilience score. This calculation embodies the essence of the proposed index, translating the multifaceted aspects of climate resilience into a coherent, quantifiable metric. In the ensuing subsections, the paper will delve deeper into the intricate relationships and mathematical models that underlie the climate resilience score calculation. This includes a rigorous explanation of how each characteristic per domain, along with their impact scores, are integrated within the overall resilience framework, ensuring a comprehensive and accurate assessment of the building's capacity to withstand climate-related challenges.

Fig. 1. Overall methodology.

Table 1
Classification of climate hazards [10].

	Temperature	Wind	Water	Solid mass
Chronic	Changing temperature	Changing wind patterns	Changing precipitation patterns	Coastal erosion
	Heat stress	Precipitation variability	Soil degradation	
	Temperature variability	Ocean acidification	Soil erosion	
	Permafrost thawing	Saline intrusion	Solifluction	
	Sea-level rise	Water stress		
Acute	Heat wave	Cyclone/Hurricane	Drought	Avalanche
	Cold wave	Storm	Heavy precipitation	Landslide
	Wildfire	Tornado	Flood	Subsidence
			Glacial lake outburst	

2.1. Climate exposure analysis

The resilience of buildings to climate-related challenges is intricately tied to their exposure to severe weather events. An illustrative statement from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) underscores the importance of “embedding information on climate risks into the architectural design, construction, and retrofitting of housing” [29]. These climate risks, which buildings must confront and withstand, encompass a wide range of direct and indirect threats. In this section, we will provide a general overview of the climate risks that buildings must address and cope with, along with an explanation of the methodology employed to utilize Numerical Weather Data for quantifying these risks.

2.1.1. Climate hazards

In the European Union, substantial endeavors have been undertaken to meticulously delineate climate hazards for the purpose of providing stakeholders with comprehensive information. According to the EU Taxonomy Classification, climate hazards are categorized as chronic and acute, further sub-divided into temperature, wind, water, and soil mass-related phenomena, as illustrated in Table 1.

In this research, the climate resilience of buildings is evaluated with respect to certain climatic phenomena, including heat waves, storms, heavy precipitation, flooding, and drought. The decision to replace “subsidence” with “cold waves” in our study, despite the Commission Delegated Regulation [30], Appendix A.II prioritizing subsidence over cold waves, is based on several critical considerations relevant to the scope and objectives of our research.

The Commission Delegated Regulation [30], Appendix A.II, identifies six priority hazards that significantly impact buildings and their users across the EU, including subsidence. However, our research focuses on direct climatic impacts on buildings’ structural and functional resilience. Subsidence, while important, is challenging to categorize

and quantify without expert soil inspections and is not a direct climatic phenomenon. Conversely, cold waves directly impact buildings’ energy efficiency, heating needs, and structural integrity due to freezing temperatures. Cold waves can increase energy demand for heating, cause water pipes to freeze and burst, and compromise structural integrity through material contraction. These effects are critical for assessing a building’s climate resilience, particularly in regions where cold waves are prevalent. Additionally, the EU-level technical guidance [10] notes that while all hazards can affect the built environment depending on location and context, six hazards are highlighted as priority due to their significant impact. Despite this, we replaced subsidence with cold waves to reflect the immediate and quantifiable climatic challenges faced by buildings in varied EU climates, ranging from very cold to very hot regions.

From the above set of climate hazards this paper focuses on six specific hazards namely heat waves, storms, heavy precipitation, flooding, drought and cold waves. These hazards have been identified as priorities due to their significant impact on buildings and their occupants, as outlined in the Commission Delegated Regulation EU2021 [30] and the EU-level technical guidance on adapting buildings to climate change [10]. Additionally, within the goal to reflect the immediate and quantifiable climatic challenges faced by buildings in varied EU climates, ranging from very cold to very hot regions, the analysis also includes the effects of cold waves as a priority hazard.

2.1.2. Climate data and exposure analysis

This subsection outlines the method for linking climate and non-climate data to assess exposure to climate hazards, employing indicators to gauge this exposure. Through defining thresholds for each hazard’s metrics, exposure is quantified on a 0 to 5 scale, where 0 indicates negligible and 5 very high exposure. This approach allows for a precise measurement of the hazard exposure level.

Table 2
Heat Waves exposure levels in Celsius.

Risk level	No risk	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Max HI	< 26.7	32.2	39.4	46.1	54.4	> 54.4

Table 3
Cold waves exposure levels.

Risk level	No risk	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Max WCI	< 4.4	-12.8	-27.2	-35.6	-50	> -50

Table 4
Heavy precipitation exposure levels.

Risk level	No risk	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Max Rainfall (mm/24 h)	< 2.5	12.7	19	32	50.8	> 50.8

Heat waves. To assess exposure to heat waves, the heat index or apparent temperature is used, which is a tool to evaluate the inhabitants thermal comfort rather than directly assessing human health impacts [31]. Developed with a focus on comfort, the heat index has become a key metric in environmental health studies for its ability to approximate exposure to heat. This makes it a crucial tool for understanding and quantifying heat wave hazards in relation to building locations. The formula to calculate the heat index was first expressed in Fahrenheit degrees [31]. In this study, the formula in degrees Celsius is used, as presented by [32]:

$$HI = c_1 + c_2T + c_3T^2 + RH(c_4 + c_5T + c_6T^2) + RH^2(c_7 + c_8T + c_9T^2) \quad (1)$$

where T is the daily maximum temperature in degrees Celsius, RH is the simultaneous relative humidity in %, and the coefficients are defined as follows:

- $c_1 = 8.7847$
- $c_2 = 1.6114$
- $c_3 = 0.012308$
- $c_4 = 2.3385$
- $c_5 = 0.14612$
- $c_6 = 2.2117 \times 10^{-3}$
- $c_7 = 0.016425$
- $c_8 = 7.2546 \times 10^{-4}$
- $c_9 = 3.582 \times 10^{-6}$

According to the National Weather Service of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of America, four levels of risk are defined based on the Heat Index, in Fahrenheit values:

- **Extreme Danger:** 130 °F or higher
- **Danger:** 105–129 °F
- **Extreme Caution:** 90–105 °F
- **Caution:** 80–90 °F

By converting these thresholds to degrees Celsius and adjusting the intermediate ranges, we derived six critical values for our study (see Table 2):

Cold waves. In the 1940s, [33] performed a series of experiments in Antarctica to measure the cooling effect of the subfreezing environment. Their research led to the development of the following formula:

$$WCI = (10.45 + 10\sqrt{V} - V) \times (33 - T_a) \quad (2)$$

where:

V represents the wind velocity in meters per second (m/s),
33 is the presumed average thermoneutral temperature of exposed

skin in degrees Celsius (°C),

T_a stands for the air temperature in degrees Celsius (°C).

The Wind Chill Index (WCI) quantifies the cooling power of the subfreezing atmosphere in complete shade, excluding the effects of evaporation. This formula was also employed in the current study to assess the exposure risk to cold conditions for both buildings and humans. According to the report [34] by the U.S. Department of Commerce/National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, exposure levels are determined based on the time an organism is at risk for frostbite. The levels are defined as follows:

- 9–17 °F: Risk of frostbite within 60 min
- -18–32 °F: Risk of frostbite within 30 min
- -33–58 °F: Risk of frostbite within 10 min
- -58 °F and below: Risk of frostbite within 5 min

This scale is adjusted using the corresponding values in Celsius and kilometers per hour (km/h) for temperature and wind speed, respectively, and intermediate thresholds are used for categorization into 5 risk levels, as shown in Table 3.

Heavy precipitation. For defining rainfall exposure/risk levels, specific universally established numbers do not exist. In a study for Alexandria, Egypt [35], thresholds were based on 1957–2012 rainfall data. Risk levels emerged from these data, categorized as: minimal risk (0–11.99 mm), low risk (12–19.99 mm), moderate risk (20–31.99 mm), and extreme risk (> 32 mm), tailored to the region. For instance, 32 mm marks the 99th percentile. In contrast, this study uses location-agnostic criteria, based on US National Center for Environmental Prediction methods [36], applied in South American rainfall estimation. Rainfall intensities and thresholds include: measurable rain (0.3 mm), light rain (2.5 mm, 6.3 mm), moderate rain (12.7 mm, 19.0 mm), and heavy rain (25.4 mm, 38.1 mm, 50.8 mm). As a result, the risk levels presented in Table 4 were derived to ensure broader applicability across different regions.

Heavy storm. For the exposure analysis in storms, we evaluated both the hourly rainfall amount (as already calculated in) and the wind speed (m/s). To select thresholds for the risk levels of wind speed, we used the Saffir-Simpson hurricane scale from the National Hurricane Center [37], developed in 1971 by civil engineer Herbert Saffir and meteorologist Robert Simpson. This scale categorizes hurricanes into 5 categories based on their hazard level, with the sole criterion being the wind speed and not considering any collateral factors such as rain, dust, etc. The categories are as follows:

- Category 1: Wind Speed 33–42 m/s
- Category 2: Wind Speed 43–49 m/s
- Category 3: Wind Speed 50–58 m/s

Table 5
Storm exposure levels.

Risk level	No risk	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Max Rainfall (mm/24 h)	< 2.5	12.7	19	32	50.8	> 50.8
Max Wind speed (m/s)	< 12	23	32	42	50	> 50

Table 6
Flooding exposure levels.

Risk level	No risk	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Max Rainfall (mm/24 h)	< 2.5	12.7	19	32	50.8	> 50.8
Distance (km)	> 5	3	1	0.5	0.1	< 0.1
Elevation (m)	> 250	100	50	30	10	< 10

Table 7
Drought exposure levels.

Drought level	Near normal	Moderately dry	Severely dry	Extremely dry
SPI values	-0.99 to 0.99	-1.0 to -1.49	-1.5 to -1.99	-2 and less

Table 8
Drought exposure levels.

Risk level	No risk	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Min SPI	> 0	-0.5	-1	-1.5	-2	< -2

- Category 4: Wind Speed 58 – 70 m/s
- Category 5: Wind Speed \geq 70 m/s

Therefore, the mapping of thresholds for the exposure assessment in storms is depicted in Table 5. It should be noted at this juncture that both conditions must simultaneously be met to categorize the exposure of the building in the worst case category.

The last three categories are classified by the US National Hurricane Center as major hurricanes. Accordingly, under this specific criterion, the Very High Risk level encompasses values from these three categories, specifically where wind speeds exceed 50 m per second. Additionally, the first two categories are designated as Moderate Risk and High Risk levels, respectively. For the No Risk level, a threshold of 12 m/s is set, below which wind poses no significant threat to humans and buildings. Typically, similar thresholds are used, such as 11.2 m/s (25 mph) by the US National Weather Service or 13.89 m/s (50 km/h) by the Irish National Meteorological Service. Consequently, 12 m/s was chosen as a rounded figure close to these common thresholds. In storm conditions, wind often accompanies other elements like rain, snow, or hail. The most frequent and severe storm phenomena typically involve strong winds coupled with heavy rainfall. Therefore, for this criterion, both rainfall amount and wind speed were selected.

Flooding. In relation to the climate hazard of flooding, three key parameters were identified that predominantly influence exposure to this hazard. Apart from the evident factor of daily rainfall amount (mm/24 h), consideration is given to the distance from bodies of water (sea, river, lake) and the elevation from sea level of the site where the reference building is situated. Regarding the thresholds for distance from the nearest body of water, the study of [38] was used, which examines settlements near rivers in various countries, based on night lights visible from satellites, and draws conclusions related to the impacts of river floods. This study analyzes the change in the distance of settlements from rivers over the years and correlates it with the impact of flooding. In this research, settlements located within 5 km of rivers did not change position over the years, unlike those with shorter distances. Therefore, the maximum threshold used will be 5 km.

In another study in the Kwara region of Nigeria [39], risk zones were delineated relative to the distance from the river water. These areas are divided into three zones: high risk for distances less than 1 kilometer, moderate risk for distances between 1 and 3 km, and low

risk for distances between 3 and 5 km. These zones were used for the risk levels of the current criterion; however, distances less than one kilometer will be divided into three levels to express extreme risks. Specifically, buildings within 100 meters are considered extremely exposed both in riverine areas and coastal areas threatened by coastal storms.

Regarding elevation from sea level, thresholds will be established based on studies related to flooding by [40,41] in the greater Mumbai area, India. The first study utilized the QGIS tool to map various elevation ranges and their correlation with flood-prone spots. Specifically, most flooding occurred within the elevation range of 5 m to 23 m. Other analyzed zones include elevations from 23 m to 100 m, 100 m to 250 m, and 250 m to 488 m. The second study mapped the area with flood hazard zones. To achieve this, factors affecting flood sensitivity were examined, with altitude being one of these factors. From the analysis, ten hazard classes were identified based on altitude in meters, as follows: 0–8, 8–11, 11–14, 14–18, 18–22, 22–27, 27–35, 35–51, 51–97, and 97–487.

Consequently, the mapping of thresholds for assessing exposure to flooding was determined to be a combination of the two studies, utilizing the low-risk areas (no risk, very low risk, low risk) from the first study, while classifying moderate to very high risk based on the second study. The results are presented in Table 6.

Drought. The exposure of the building to the drought hazard was estimated using the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI). This index, proposed by experts in 2009 at the Interregional Workshop on Indices and Early Warning Systems for Drought, was recommended for adoption by all National Meteorological and Hydrological Services (NMHSs) worldwide [42]. Its purpose is to characterize meteorological droughts, supplementing other existing drought indices utilized within their respective services.

As per the official guide of the Standardized Precipitation Index, the thresholds for drought exposure classification are defined, as presented in Table 7. However, in order to uphold scaling within the range of 0 to 5, the thresholds for drought exposure classification listed in Table 8 were employed in this study.

2.1.3. Weight calculation

After calculating a building's exposure to the climate risks outlined in this study, the next step entails evaluating the severity and likelihood of these risks. This is accomplished by assigning suitable weights

Table 9
Hazard Categories and Indices.

Hazard	Heat waves	Cold waves	Heavy precipitation	Storms	Flooding	Drought
j	1	2	3	4	5	6

to each risk, reflecting their significance. These weights are specific to each climate hazard and are integrated in the calculation of the building's climate resilience index. The process of assigning weights for each climate hazard is initiated with the creation of Table 9. This table correlates each climate hazard with a value, denoted as ' j '.

Let e_j denote the result of the exposure analysis, as derived from the methodology detailed in 2.1.2, for each hazard. Subsequently, these results are normalized using the equation provided in (3).

$$\bar{e}_j = \frac{e_j}{\max(e_j)} \quad (3)$$

At this stage, the injection of external importance to each hazard, tailored to the assessor's requirements, becomes feasible. Thus, i_j ' is defined for each climate hazard ' j ' and must adhere to (4).

$$0 \leq i_j \leq 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_j i_j = 1 \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the non-normalized intermediate weights, w_j , for each climate hazard j are computed using Eq. (5).

$$w_j = i_j \cdot \bar{e}_j \quad (5)$$

Finally, the weights are normalized using Eq. (6).

$$\bar{w}_j = \frac{w_j}{\sum_{i=1}^6 w_i} \quad (6)$$

2.2. Building's climate resilience impact assessment

In the followings we explore how specific design and infrastructure considerations can contribute to building resilience in the context of the identified climate hazards and define a set of criteria based on which the climate resilience of the building is assessed. The criteria correspond to specific building characteristics, which are classified into six domains, these are: the building envelope, the energy and water systems, adaptation solutions throughout the building's infrastructure, sustainability practices and actions related to the buildings functional and environmental performance throughout its lifespan. To understand the climate resilience of buildings and their protection against severe climate events, it is essential to segment the building into domains. This segmentation allows for an in-depth analysis of how the characteristics of each domain influence the building's resilience to the specific climate hazards. The detailed impact scores assigned to each domain attribute are thoroughly documented in the supplementary material, Section 2. Notably, our methodology exhibits similarities with the SRI calculation method, as previously outlined. Specifically, our approach involves segmenting the building into distinct domains and, within those domains, identifying various features/systems (akin to the services defined in the SRI framework). The configuration of these features/systems plays a pivotal role in determining the building's climate resilience. Subsequent sections will elaborate on the domains and their associated features/systems, providing a comprehensive overview of the components considered in our assessment.

2.2.1. Building envelope

The building envelope plays a crucial role in augmenting the resilience of structures against climatic challenges, employing both active and passive techniques to mitigate the impact of environmental conditions. This role is pivotal not only in enhancing structural durability but also in managing the rate of material degradation, as highlighted by recent studies [43]. A comprehensive examination of the building envelope's components reveals their varying contributions to climate resilience. These components encompass wall construction materials,

interlayer insulation, and external wall insulation, alongside roof insulation strategies. Moreover, the analysis extends to the window-to-wall ratio, examining its influence on thermal efficiency, as well as the implementation of advanced glazing systems and shutters designed to optimize energy performance and withstand extreme weather conditions. This multifaceted approach underscores the significance of each element within the building envelope in contributing to the overall climate resilience of the structure. For a deeper insight into these components and their efficacy, Table A.1 categorizes each building envelope characteristic, ranking the alternatives from the least to the most effective.

In evaluating materials and construction techniques for enhancing building climate resilience, we rely on the comprehensive assessment provided by [44], which delineates the influence of diverse and evolving European regulatory frameworks on construction methodologies. The analysis draws upon the thermal transmittance criteria, alongside considerations of air and humidity tightness and sustainability, as discussed in [45] and further elaborated upon by [46], highlighting the vulnerability of buildings to extreme weather events due to older construction technologies. The paper categorizes wall construction techniques from less to more resilient, noting the advancements in thermal resistance and durability. The role of interlayer insulation in the building envelope's defense against climatic challenges is explored, emphasizing the variability in regulatory standards across Europe and the impact of insulation materials and application techniques on thermal transmittance and building resilience, as noted by [44,47,48], and [49]. These sources collectively underscore the importance of evolving construction practices in enhancing building strength against environmental pressures. External wall insulation, as discussed by [50, 51], and [52], is identified as a critical component for fortifying buildings against extreme weather, improving energy efficiency, and mitigating risks of air and water ingress, with [53] providing a classification of various insulation materials and methods in terms of their effectiveness in enhancing climate resilience. The examination of roofing materials reveals the significant impact of insulation and material choices on a building's thermal performance and resistance to climatic hazards. The assessment ranges from traditional asphalt shingles to innovative solutions like green and hurricane-resistant roofs, illustrating the technological evolution aimed at optimizing energy efficiency and climate resilience. The analysis extends to the window-to-wall ratio, where [54] establishes the optimal range for balancing solar radiation absorption and repulsion, demonstrating how deviations from this range affect a building's thermal efficiency and resilience to temperature extremes. Lastly, the importance of shutters in augmenting a building's defense against environmental challenges is highlighted, with [55,56] examining their role in thermal regulation, water diversion, and protection from storm damage.

2.2.2. Energy systems

Energy systems and services are foundational to enhancing a building's resilience against climate-induced hazards. By proposing a comprehensive rating approach, this paper evaluates the resilience imparted by various energy systems, including cooling equipment, heating systems, ventilation mechanisms, and the incorporation of energy-efficient and smart appliances. For a deeper insight into these components and their efficacy, Table A.2 categorizes each energy system characteristic, ranking the alternatives from the least to the most effective. The assessment of cooling strategies' resilience is based on the analysis outlined in [57]. This study undertakes an in-depth examination of the performance of state-of-the-art cooling strategies, with a particular focus on their effectiveness during heatwaves and power

outages. To gain a more comprehensive insight into the characteristics of each cooling system, we have drawn upon information from the U.S. Department [58] (DOE). Insights on the assessment of different heating technologies are retrieved by the papers of [59,60]. For residential usage, the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) website was also advised. As outlined in the study of [59] the site's climatic conditions, expected thermal comfort, costs, the availability of energy sources and the application of the building are key factors that affect the performance and scoring of each heating technology. Also, ergonomic, environmental, reliability, technical, and economical aspects should be considered [60]. For ventilation systems, the scoring is based on the articles of [61,62]. [61] focus on natural ventilation and examine the capacity of different natural ventilation strategies to deliver heatwave resilience and sufficient thermal comfort and maintain high indoor air quality within warm climatic conditions. The study of [62] expands the results of [61] and offers a systematic review to compare both natural and mechanical ventilation systems under a sustainable design perspective. Last, we recognize the resilience benefits of the strategic deployment of energy efficiency and automated building monitoring and management systems [63]. To evaluate the use of energy-efficient appliances, a 10-point scale is employed, which represents the percentage of such appliances within a building. This same method is applied to assess smart appliances. Energy-efficient appliances are considered those achieving a rating higher than C on the new A-G EU energy label scale of [64]. Smart appliances are those equipped with smart features capable of sensing, actuating, and communicating via the internet [65].

2.2.3. Adaptation solutions on systems and services

In addressing the adaptation of buildings to the priority hazards delineated in Section 2.2, this section compiles a range of potential solutions, analyzing their alignment and interaction with the identified hazards as per the methodology articulated in the European Commission report [10]. The assessment of these solutions employs a multifaceted approach to gauge their efficacy and presence within the subject buildings. Primarily, a two-tiered evaluation framework is utilized, categorizing solutions as either present or absent in the analyzed structures. This binary assessment serves to succinctly identify which adaptive measures are already in place, thereby facilitating a straightforward analysis of existing resilience levels. However, the evaluation methodology diverges when it comes to the installation of storm protection devices, adopting a more nuanced three-tiered scoring system. This approach assigns differential scores based on the proportion of critical building devices that are fortified with storm protection measures. Such a grading system acknowledges the varying degrees of vulnerability and protective needs across different building components, thereby offering a more detailed and tailored assessment of storm resilience capabilities. The specific adaptation solutions, alongside their corresponding evaluations, are listed in Table A.3.

2.2.4. Sustainability practices

Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) are natural solutions designed to retain a specific percentage of rainfall, effectively accommodating water for short durations and mitigating heavy precipitation events. There are a variety of different SuDS options, each serving different purposes and their development is dependent on the different locations or typical rainfall landing area. Under the 2019 version of the UK National Planning Policy Framework [66], SuDS form one of five key considerations to the provision of development, when considering how to manage flood risk. Also, the use of SuDS as a central tool to reduce flooding was outlined in the Pitt Review [67]. Depending on their design, SuDS can enhance biodiversity and reduce the risk of sewage overflow and associated health hazards, and vegetation, as part of SuDS, contributes to heat reduction. However, they require regular and potentially costly maintenance. The types of SuDS that are examined here are: permeable surfaces and filter drains (gravelled area, solid

pavins blocks, porous paviers), infiltration devices (soakaways, infiltration trenches and basins), filter strips and swales, basins and ponds (constructed wetlands, balancing ponds, detention basins, retention ponds) and living roofs. The hierarchy of the different SuDS types is based on a sustainability scale and incorporates associated amenity and environmental benefits as in [68].

2.2.5. Water systems

The assessment of water systems within the framework of building resilience and sustainability focuses on two characteristics. The first characteristic involves the inspection of anti-return valves in toilets and sinks, as well as sewage pumps, to determine their presence or absence. This assessment is crucial for mitigating contamination risks, ensuring that these systems are designed to prevent the backflow of sewage and potentially contaminated water into clean water supplies. The second aspect under scrutiny is the incorporation of rainwater tanks, a key element in sustainable water management. These tanks play a significant role in collecting and storing rainwater for reuse, reducing dependency on municipal water supplies and enhancing the building's resilience to water scarcity. By systematically assessing these characteristics, this research provides a comprehensive understanding of the resilience and sustainability of water systems, in line with established principles in building evaluations.

2.2.6. Site & location

The resilience of a building extends beyond its physical structure to encompass the broader context of its site and location, including the development of the surrounding area and the infrastructure available to withstand extreme weather events. In addressing land use and zoning within the context of urban development, our analysis leans on the insights provided by [69], which frames land-use planning as a pivotal element in mitigating climate-related hazards. This perspective is instrumental in structuring our criterion into five distinct levels, aimed at categorizing land use strategies based on their effectiveness in addressing and adapting to climate challenges. Furthermore, the critical importance of utilities and infrastructure in the resilience of urban areas to climate hazards is examined, with an emphasis on the essential role of emergency services, healthcare facilities, and well-conceived evacuation strategies. As outlined by [70], these components are fundamental in ensuring rapid response capabilities, effective crisis management, and sustained care during climate emergencies. This multifaceted approach underscores the necessity of integrating robust infrastructure planning with urban development initiatives to safeguard communities against the evolving landscape of climate hazards.

2.3. Climate resilience score calculation

Based on the above classification of building domains and their respective characteristics, a methodology has been developed to assess building resilience against climate hazards. The detailed list of characteristics considered for each domain is presented in Tables 10 and 11. The methodology used to adaptively calculate and assess the climate resilience of buildings in relation to the specific climate hazards they face is outlined in this paragraph. For ease of reference in the equations that follow, the different components of the buildings are mapped to the y and z indices in Tables 10 and 11, respectively.

Let $C_{z,y,j}$ be the resilience score achieved by the reference building for component y of category z against hazard j . Each score $C_{z,y,j}$ is normalized by the maximum resilience score that the reference building achieves among all components y of category z against hazard j .

$$\bar{C}_{z,y,j} = \frac{C_{z,y,j}}{C_{z,y,j}^{\max}} \quad (7)$$

By summing up the normalized values of the score in each component y of each category z for each hazard j as, the overall climate resilience

Table 10
Building Categories and components indices, Part 1.

$\begin{matrix} z \\ y \end{matrix}$	Envelope (1)	Energy Systems (2)	Resilience (3)
1	Walls	Cooling Equipment	Connection between surface water & sewage
2	In. insulation	Heating Equipment	Placement of electrical & mechanical systems
3	Roof Insulation	Ventilation	Drainage network dimensioning
4	Window/Wall ratio	EE appliances	Placement of toilets & sinks
5	Glazing system	Smart appliances	Water efficient fixtures and fittings
6	Ex. Insulation		Greywater recycling
7	Shutters		Water storage
8			Burial of distribution lines
9			Installation of backup generators
10			Storm protection devices

Table 11
Building Categories and components indices, Part 2.

$\begin{matrix} z \\ y \end{matrix}$	Sustainability Practices (4)	Water Systems (5)	Site & Location (6)
1	Sustainable urban drainage systems	Anti-return valves	Land use and zoning
2		Rainwater tanks	Emergency services, hospitals, and evacuation route setups

score is generated in a scale from 0 to 1.

$$S_j = \frac{\sum_z \sum_y \bar{C}_{z,y,j}}{N} \quad (8)$$

Then, the normalized weights calculated in (6) are incorporated through (9) to account for the intensity of the building’s exposure to the considered climate hazards.

$$WS_j = NWS_j \cdot \bar{w}_j \quad (9)$$

Finally, by summing the resilience score for each climate hazard j , the total climate resilience score of the reference building on a scale of 0 to 1 is obtained, which is ultimately multiplied by 100 to yield the percentage resilience score of the reference building against the optimal scenario.

$$S_{total} = \sum_{j=1}^6 WS_j \quad (10)$$

3. Case study

3.1. Pilot buildings

To thoroughly assess and evaluate the robustness of our methodology, it has been applied to two distinct buildings located in countries with differing climate conditions: Finland and Greece. The choice of these locations offers a diverse range of environmental challenges due to their contrasting climate profiles, providing a comprehensive test bed for our approach. Finland is characterized by cold and harsh winters, presenting unique challenges for building resilience, primarily in terms of thermal insulation and energy efficiency. Conversely, Greece experiences a Mediterranean climate, marked by hot, dry summers and mild winters. By applying and evaluating our methodology in these two buildings, each with distinct location and building characteristics, we can validate its versatility and effectiveness in enhancing building resilience against a wide spectrum of climate hazards. This dual application allows us to refine our approach, ensuring it is robust enough to accommodate diverse geographical and climatic contexts and can be generalized to other regions with different environmental conditions. The detailed list of construction characteristics and their systems for both case study buildings is presented in Table A.4.

Helsinki - Finland. The climate of Finland exhibits characteristics of both maritime and continental climates, depending on the direction of air flow. Despite its northern location, the average temperature in Finland is several degrees higher than that of most other regions at similar latitudes. The Finnish climate is characterized by irregular

precipitation and it often experiences swift changes in weather conditions [71]. Additionally, Finland is expected to witness an increase in both humidity and temperature, with the most significant warming occurring during the winter months. Winters are projected to become more humid, overcast, and with reduced snowfall, as highlighted in the study by [72]. The rise in sea level, estimated to be 29 cm in the Gulf of Finland, is partially compensated by the residual land mass uplifting still following the loss of ice cover from the last ice age [73]. The main climate-related hazards in Finland are storms, floods and rapid flooding in or near the population centers [74].

Our study is carried out in a large office building, used and operated by the City of Helsinki. The City of Helsinki is actively focusing on the enhancement of data-driven management for its portfolio of city-owned buildings. This particular building was finalized in 2020, covering an area of 35,261m² across seven floors and a basement and can accommodate approximately 2000 people. The building is part of district heating and district cooling networks. These networks are currently powered by coal, but there are plans to transition to gas and biomass as alternative fuel sources.

Athens - Greece. To further broaden the analysis, the second application was conducted in Greece, a country situated in Southeast Europe. Greece exhibits a diverse climate owing to its unique geographical location and varied topography, resulting in distinct climatic zones within relatively short distances [75]. Climate hazards in Greece are primarily influenced by its Mediterranean climate, characterized by mild and wet winters in the southern lowland and island regions, contrasted with cold winters with heavy snowfalls in the mountainous areas in the central and northern regions, alongside hot and dry summers [76]. These climate related hazards include heatwaves, droughts, wildfires and occasional winter storms and flooding. Our methodology is implemented in a ground floor office building of 150 m² located on the campus of National Technical University of Athens.

3.2. Exposure and weight results

As outlined in the framework detailed in Section 2.1.2, the meteorological data for each pilot site were drawn from the open-access repository [77] and subsequently analyzed. Figs. 2 and 3 demonstrate the variation in the indicators considered in this manuscript over the years 2020–2022. Specifically, Fig. 2 provides a comparative analysis of temperature-related indices — namely, the HI and the WCI — for Athens and Helsinki. The daily HI range (Fig. 2(a)) reveals that Athens endures ‘high’ to ‘very high’ heat exposure levels during the summer, consistent with typical heat wave conditions, whereas Helsinki remains within ‘low’ to ‘moderate’ levels year-round. This contrast highlights

(a) Variation of daily HI over time in Athens and Helsinki.

(b) Variation of daily WCI over time between Athens and Helsinki.

Fig. 2. Comparative analysis of temperature-related indices (HI and WCI) in Athens and Helsinki across three years (2020–2022).

(a) Daily rainfall rates in Athens and Helsinki.

(b) Variation of SPI for Athens and Helsinki.

Fig. 3. Comparative analysis of hydrological metrics (rainfall and SPI) in Athens and Helsinki across three years (2020–2022).

the relative severity of heat hazards faced by Athens, underscoring the importance of the HI as a metric for assessing thermal comfort and potential heat stress, particularly in urban environments. The daily WCI range (Fig. 2(b)) illustrates how wind chill significantly lowers the perceived temperature in both cities during winter months. Helsinki’s WCI dips into the ‘high’ risk exposure zone, suggesting more pronounced cold stress due to the combined effects of low temperatures and wind. This finding validates the WCI’s application in quantifying cold wave hazards, particularly in regions with harsh winter conditions. Hydrological metrics are assessed in Fig. 3, with daily rainfall rates (Fig. 3(a)) indicating a more pronounced variability in Helsinki, implying a greater exposure to heavy precipitation events. The SPI data (Fig. 3(b)) occasionally indicates moderate drought conditions for Athens, as reflected by the SPI’s negative values, aligning with the predetermined drought exposure levels. Such insights from the SPI are crucial for understanding temporal drought patterns and enhancing drought resilience.

Following the analysis of the weather data combined with the analysis of the spatial layout of the area, (elevation, distance from water bodies), the resulting weights, derived from equations ((3), (4) and (6)), are concisely presented in Table 12. A divergence in climate hazards between the two locations emerges from the data. Helsinki, situated in a Scandinavian country, grapples with the challenges of intensely cold winters, which is well-reflected in the ‘high’ risk ratings on the WCI. The city’s normal humidity levels, alongside moderate rainfall, reduce the risk of heatwaves and heavy precipitation, yet the presence of these factors cannot be disregarded. Limited storm events are another characteristic of the Helsinki site, hinting at a lesser risk of storm-induced exposure. Conversely, Athens confronts hot and arid summers, significantly heightening its susceptibility to drought, as indicated by the SPI trends. Its winters, while milder compared to Helsinki’s, still present climate hazards, albeit of a different nature. The occurrence of storms and heavier rainfall instances in Athens marks a notable risk for flooding, necessitating careful consideration in urban planning and hazard preparedness. Fig. 4 compares the assigned weights for these

Table 12
Pilot applications weight results.

Pilot case	Heat waves	Cold waves	Heavy precipitation	Storms	Flooding	Drought
Helsinki	0.08	0.31	0.23	0.15	0.15	0.08
Athens	0.29	0.14	0.14	0.07	0.21	0.14

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis of weight results for Helsinki and Athens.

climate hazards in both locations, offering a stark visual representation of their contrasting climatic challenges. These weights provide actionable insights, informing risk mitigation and adaptation strategies, and are integral to the climate resilience assessment of the buildings.

The criteria outlined in Tables 10 and 11 have been fulfilled for both buildings. In Fig. 5(a), the total score attained by each building within the climate resilience framework is presented. It is evident that the building located in Finland demonstrates superior reinforcement against the severe weather events to which it is exposed, compared to the building situated in Greece. Shifting focus to Fig. 5(b), the discernible difference is primarily observed in the energy systems and building envelope components. This discrepancy can be readily explained by the Finnish building being a more modern construction than its Greek counterpart.

By examining Figs. 6(a) and 6(b), insights into the resilience of the buildings against their respective hazards are obtained. Specifically, in Fig. 6(a), it is observed that the building in Finland achieves a comparable resilience score against all climate hazards, nearing 50%, and notably excels in drought, heavy precipitation, and cold waves, where the resilience score approaches 60%. Conversely, the Greek case demonstrates good resilience against flood, drought, and heavy precipitation, achieving a score close to 50%. However, it appears to lag in resilience against storms, cold waves, and heat waves, where the resilience score is just above 30%. Lastly, in Fig. 6(a), the weighted resilience of each building reference to each hazard contributes to the overall score. By aggregating the percentages for each hazard, the total score is obtained, as described in (10).

3.3. Comparative simulations

Fig. 7(a) illustrates how building envelope configurations influence building resilience against climate hazards. We consider seven core building envelope elements (Table 10) with varying configurations that impact resilience differently for each hazard. All other building components remain fixed, reflecting the pilot buildings' actual characteristics. Similarly Fig. 7(b) depicts the results of simulations with energy systems with varying level of resilience among the identified

hazards. Similar to the building envelope simulations, all other building components are fixed.

As expected, the CRI increases for both pilots in both figures when applying more resilient building configurations. Notably, the impact of specific solutions in the building characteristics differs between the pilots. Specifically, differences in the buildings' resilience between the pilots are more significant in the simulated scenarios for energy systems compared to the building envelope alterations. This is because some energy systems primarily mitigate specific hazards, particularly heat and cold waves. These hazards, as Fig. 4 reveals, exhibit the greatest disparity in impact between the pilot locations due to their unique climates. In contrast, building envelope elements influence the resilience to a wider range of climate hazards with a more consistent effect across hazard types.

To delve deeper into the weighting methodology's influence on tool adaptability, a second set of simulations is conducted. In this scenario, the weights assigned to each pilot location (representing the prevalence of specific climate hazards) were swapped. Essentially, we analyzed how the same building would perform under the climate hazard profiles of Athens and Helsinki.

The results (Fig. 8) show that each pilot building exhibited significantly different resilience scores when evaluated with the contrasting weights, reflecting the varying hazard intensities of their respective locations. Notably, the Finnish building demonstrated increased resilience when evaluated under the Greek climate hazards. This suggests that its design characteristics offer greater resilience in that context, potentially recommending similar building practices for Greece. Conversely, the Greek pilot building displayed lower resilience under Finnish climate conditions. This analysis also allows for the extraction of specific conclusions regarding individual building elements. Importantly, as observed previously, the most significant differences arise in the case of energy systems.

The above results show the importance of the proposed weighting methodology. It enables the tool to capture the differential effects of building characteristics on pilots with varying vulnerabilities to specific climate hazards. This demonstrates the tool's capability in assessing both overall building adaptability and the impact of individual element changes on climate resilience.

4. Discussion and limitations

The proposed approach conducts a detailed assessment of building components under various climate hazards, integrating resilience adaptation measures. The intention of this section is to evaluate the developed methodologies towards two primary goals and identify key limitations. The first goal is the creation of a robust resilience rating approach, grounded in a high-level assessment of climate vulnerability. The second goal refers to the importance of the evaluation's user-friendliness, making it accessible to building residents or users without necessitating technical knowledge or complex input retrieval methodologies. The paper successfully maintains a balanced trade off between the two goals, namely the accuracy of the rating approach and ease of use.

For the first goal, the initial stage of the climate resilience assessment involves identifying related climate hazards and evaluating the buildings' exposure to them, considering both present and future conditions. In contrast to previous analyses which are either limited to a small number of hazards or focus only on natural disasters and not on climate related hazards, here hazards are retrieved by the EU taxonomy

(a) Comparison of overall climate resilience scores for pilot buildings in Athens and Helsinki.

(b) Breakdown of climate resilience scores by category for pilot buildings in Athens and Helsinki.

Fig. 5. Comparison of climate resilience scores.

(a) Comparison of weighted climate resilience scores by climate hazard for pilot buildings in for Athens and Helsinki.

(b) Comparison of non-weighted climate resilience scores by climate hazard for pilot buildings in for Athens and Helsinki.

Fig. 6. Comparative evaluation of weighted and non-weighted climate resilience scores by climate hazard for Athens and Helsinki.

(a) Comparison of simulated climate resilience scores and their differences within the building envelope domain for buildings in Athens and Helsinki.

(b) Comparison of simulated climate resilience scores and their differences within the energy systems domain for buildings in Athens and Helsinki.

Fig. 7. Comparative analysis of simulated climate resilience scores on building envelope and energy systems domain for Athens and Helsinki.

Fig. 8. Overall methodology.

and selected based on their applicability to the examined locations. The results from the exposure analysis are used to calculate appropriate weights for each applicable hazard, reflecting their importance and likelihood for the specific building or location. Here, noteworthy limitations are acknowledged related to the geographical and contextual variability of climate hazards and mitigation measures. The overall climate resilience score of the building is derived from the resilience scoring of key building components, initially aggregated within three categories: the building envelope, energy systems, and any existing or planned adaptation measures aimed at enhancing the building's resilience. As most studies and tools lack a clear methodology for rating the building indicators, the identification of the scoring methodology for the provision of the resilience rating was a significant challenge. To address this, an extensive literature review was conducted to establish a resilience metric for each building component under the identified hazards. Obtaining scores for each building component and across different scales of building characteristics emerged as a crucial aspect of the analysis. This not only allows for flexibility in proposing detailed guidelines and requirements for incorporation into the building design, but also enhances the efficiency of adaptation actions in withstanding, responding to, and recovering from disruptions caused by extreme climate conditions, which also contributes to maximizing the interconnected economic and social benefits.

At this stage it is acknowledged that accuracy of data entry is highly dependent on the expertise of the person conducting the assessment. The assessment might not fully capture the influence of complex factors related to individual building components and their interactions. Additionally, it may not accurately predict future performance, which can be impacted by factors like changing climate and occupancy patterns. For improved model performance, expert input on specific data points would be valuable. For instance, regarding the building envelope, details on wall thickness and construction materials, along with an evaluation of structural wear and tear, would be beneficial. Similarly, for energy systems, an assessment of the performance of cooling and heating systems within each identified technology, and for the evaluation of smart appliances and their energy efficiency, a more detailed evaluation scale incorporating metrics or equipment to measure the actual impact, would improve accuracy of results. Finally,

regarding adaptation solutions, expanding the current evaluation scale with more detailed gradations based on factors like building location and size would also enhance the assessment. However, it is crucial to find a balance between detailed data collection and user-friendliness. Thus, the proposed methodology aims to maintain a level of detail that promotes user-friendliness. This user-centric approach is validated by the two case studies, where no difficulties were encountered in user engagement or data collection.

5. Conclusions and future work

Climate risks in urban areas are increasing, underscoring the significance of strategic decisions in designing and implementing the new urban environment towards the worldwide effort for climate resilient, low-emission development. Among the various studies on cities' climate resilience, this research focuses on the climate resilience assessment of buildings. The proposed framework constitutes of a detailed climate exposure analysis and vulnerability assessment, facilitating the identification and measurement of key climate hazards. An efficient monitoring of these hazards is essential for policy stakeholders in implementing necessary adaptation actions, plans, and policies to exert control.

To address uncertainties related to hazard realization over a building's expected lifespan, a sensitivity analysis of hazard weights calculation is important. This could reflect future regional climate projections and environmental factors, offering insights into the probability of hazard occurrence, and influencing likelihood levels. At this field, future discussions should center on the continuous updating of climate projections and adapting modeling results to changing weather values. Considerations for uncertainty analysis involve implementing the methodology across various time horizons to capture varying levels of input data uncertainty in the modeling results. Simultaneously, it is essential to assess the quality of data and the effort required for their collection.

To address limitations related to geographic variability and allow for more granular analysis, the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) tools is recommended. These tools can be used for mapping and tailored risk assessment with focus on specific hazards depending on the building location or a specific part of the building, for example rooms with more vulnerable occupants or important equipment. This

Table A.1
Building envelope characteristics.

Walls	Interlayer insulation	Roof insulation	W/W ratio	Glazing system	External insulation	Shutters
Single-layer unreinforced masonry walls	None	None	<0.2, >0.6	Single-Pane, Non-Energy-Efficient Windows	None	None
Lightweight timber/Gypsum Board walls	Air gap between studs	Poorly insulated roof	0.2	Double-Pane Windows (Non-Low Emissivity) with Poor Sealing	Styrofoam or EPS Board on Exterior	Temporary Plywood Panels or Cardboard
Basic wood framing	Fiberglass batt insulation between studs	Asphalt Shingles or Low-Quality Roofing Material	0.6	Standard Double-Pane Low-Emissivity (Low-E) Windows	Exterior Mineral Wool (Rock Wool) Insulation	Accordion-style Shutters
Brick or concrete block walls	Cellulose insulation between studs	Standard Insulated Roof with Asphalt Shingles	0.3	Triple-Pane Low-E Windows with Improved Sealing	Exterior Insulated Finish Systems (EIFS)	Roll-Down or Roll-Up Shutters
reinforced concrete/steel framing with masonry/concrete block cladding	Spray foam insulation (open-cell) between studs	Metal Roof with Insulation	0.5	Impact-Resistant Windows with Double or Triple Panes	Exterior Aerogel Insulation	Storm Panels (Metal or Polycarbonate)
Reinforced concrete/steel framing with resilient siding materials	spray foam insulation (closed-cell) between studs	Solar Reflective or Cool Roof	0.4	Hurricane-Resistant Windows with Laminated Glass	Current level	Bahama Shutters
Structural Insulated panels	Interior insulating sheathing	Green (Vegetative) Roof	–	Dynamic Glazing with Low-E Coatings	Impact-Resistant Windows and Doors	–
Aerogel insulation	–	Hurricane-Resistant Roofing	–	–	–	–

would enable a more detailed analysis for each building indicator. Furthermore, while the identified building components proved sufficient for this research, additional established building evaluation methodologies could be incorporated to further enhance results and expand the analysis. Examples include the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC), the SRI, and the Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE). Exploring synergies and interactions between the proposed methodology and these established indicators would facilitate a more comprehensive building assessment.

As ultimate goal, to increase the impact of the proposed methodology, it is essential to generate outputs that can be easily translated into actions for enhancing resilience. Recommendations for adaptation actions should be tailored to user groups, clustered, and results should be provided for a set of buildings or areas. Among the goals for future research is to integrate these results in a web application designed to improve the methodology's user-friendliness and expand its accessibility to individuals interested in utilizing it. As a general remark, related approaches should allow for a range of inputs to reflect variability in resources, technical expertise, and available information. The ability to be fully adaptable for different purposes, while still providing a detailed methodology, is a key feature lacking from today's research.

Lastly, it is important to highlight that, in parallel with resilience assessment, buildings should minimize their impact on the environment by reducing energy consumption and mitigating contributions to greenhouse gas emissions. In this endeavor, engaging the necessary stakeholders capable of influencing households' behavioral changes and supporting businesses in their low-carbon transition is crucial.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Efstathios Stamatopoulos: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Aikaterini Forouli:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Daniela Stoian:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Panagiotis Kouloukakis:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Elissaios Sarmas:** Writing

– review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Vangelis Marinakis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

We confirm that we have given due consideration to the protection of intellectual property associated with this work and that there are no impediments to publication, including the timing of publication, with respect to intellectual property. In so doing we confirm that we have followed the regulations of our institutions concerning intellectual property.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

The work presented is based on research conducted within the framework of the Horizon Europe European Commission project DigiBUILD (Grant Agreement No. 101069658). The authors would like to thank all the DigiBUILD consortium partners for their fruitful discussions, remarks and observations. Additionally, we extend our gratitude to Petteri Rekoma from Forum Virium Helsinki for providing the building data used in the Finland case study. The content of the paper is the sole responsibility of its authors and does not necessary reflect the views of the EC. We thank the anonymous reviewers for helpful feedback and comments.

Appendix A. Tables

See [Tables A.1–A.4](#).

Table A.2
Energy systems characteristics.

Cooling system	Heating system	Ventilation	Use of energy-efficient appliances (%)	Use of smart appliances (%)
None	None	None	None	None
Passive cooling	Gravity air furnaces	Single-sided and cross ventilation	10	10
Radiant cooling/Evaporative cooling	Portable or plug-in space heaters	Windcatchers	20	20
Fans(Ceiling Fans, Window Fans, and Other Circulating Fans, whole house fans)	Electric resistance	Solar Chimneys	30	30
Mini-split, window and portable air conditioners	Hot water baseboard heater systems	Natural ventilation with Evaporative cooling	40	40
Water cooling	None	Air handling units (AHU)	50	50
District cooling network	In-floor radiant	Heat recovery ventilation	60	60
Central air conditioning systems	Traditional boilers and radiator systems	Hybrid or mixed mode ventilation(natural and mechanical ventilation)	70	70
Geothermal cooling	Heat pump	–	80	80
Hybrid (geothermal - district cooling)	District heating network	–	90	90
–	Forced air distribution systems, furnace	–	100	100
–	Hybrid heating systems	–	–	–

Table A.3
Types of adaptation solutions.

Adaptation solutions
Connection between surface water & sewage
Placement of electrical & mechanical systems
Drainage network dimensioning
Placement of toilets & sinks
Water efficient fixtures and fittings
Greywater recycling
Water storage
Burial of distribution lines
Installation of backup generators
Storm protection devices

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Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111869>.

Table A.4
Detailed features of pilot buildings in Finland and Greece.

Domain	Finland	Greece
Building Envelope	Structural insulated panels, aerogel insulation, standard insulated roof with asphalt shingles, triple-panel low fenestration, roll-down shutters	Reinforced concrete/steel framing with concrete block cladding, air gap between studs, asphalt shingles roofing material, double-panel windows, roll-down shutters
Energy Systems	District cooling network, district heating network, heat recovery ventilation, 70% use of smart appliances, 90% energy efficient appliances	Air conditioners, electric resistance, air handling units, 30% use of smart appliances in the building, 30% use of energy-efficient appliances
Resilience Measures	Disconnected surface water from sewage, electrical and mechanical systems and utilities above flood level, drainage network dimensioned to future runoff projections, placement of sinks/toilet at a minimum height, above flood level, burial of distribution lines, surge protection for less than 50% of devices	Disconnect surface water from sewage, electrical and mechanical systems and utilities above flood level, drainage network dimensioned to future runoff projections, placement of sinks/toilet at a minimum height, above flood level, burial of distribution lines, backup generators, surge protection devices
Sustainability Practices	Permeable surfaces and filter drains	Permeable surfaces and filter drains
Site & Location	Urban sprawl with limited green spaces, well-equipped hospitals and trained emergency personnel	Mixed-use zoning with green corridors, limited or underfunded emergency services

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